

Nutritional Solution challenges in the face of Climate change through Improve Agricultural Interventions on finger Millets cultivation among the Tribal community of Koraput district.

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Abstract

Irrigated agricultural lands have been decreasing which enhance the focus of researchers on dry lands to further increase grain production. Due to low fertility, utilization of dry lands to produce sufficient quality grains is a big challenge. Millets as climate resilient crops over other grains such as wheat and rice in terms of marginal growing conditions and high nutritional value. These nutri-cereals has vitamins, minerals, essential fatty acids, phyto-chemicals and antioxidants that can help to eradicate many nutritional deficiency diseases. Millets cultivation can keep dry lands productive and ensure future food and nutritional security. Koraput is one of the tribal dominated districts of Odisha in India and recently declared as one of the agro-biodiversity hot spots in India. Different millets have been frequently used as traditional foods by the tribal people of Koraput, and the uses are diverse. The study focused on different agricultural interventions for enhancement of millet production in Koraput. In which SMI was 12-14 quintals per hectare which was more than double the average yields from traditional method. This was a substantial motivating factor for farmers to adopt SMI, though initially farmers were skeptical that SMI is labour intensive. As transplanting facilitates inter-row and interplant weed control, farmers used weeding tools like roller weeder to incorporate the weeds into the soil, boosting fertility. Aerating the soil stimulated the growth of plant roots, making them strong enough to resist heavy winds from lodging. The average production system highest shows in case of SMI in comparison to LT and Tradition methods, so that the SMI process in case of millet cultivation definitely boost the millet production system among the tribal community of Koraput.

Keywords: *Finger millets; Koraput; Agricultural intervention; SMI; Broadcasting; Sustainable agriculture*

Introduction

Development in scientific technological innovations led humanity into another level of modernization. In agriculture, strategies on technological innovations, viz. development and selection of high yielding variety, use of synthetic fertilizers and pesticides, mechanization and irrigation facilities, have resulted in sufficient availability of food. Crop production is dependent to various abiotic and biotic stresses that are made more adverse by climatic factors. Improved agronomic practices and cultivation of stress tolerant varieties can sustain production in changing climatic condition [1]

Finger millet is a major staple food crop, second to paddy, among subsistence farming households in the rainfed uplands of Koraput district in South Odisha [3]. The finger millet, contributing to the food and nutritional security of the tribal households in Koraput, under extreme weather conditions as mentioned in the table 1 Finger millet is resilient to a variety of agro-climatic adversities, such as poor soil fertility and drought conditions, and it requires low inputs. The tribal people are traditionally cultivated the millets especially in upland region. Finger millet seeds can resist storage pests and it is the optional food for tribal by ensuring year-round food supply during crop failure also. Millets fall under the group of C4 cereals. C4 cereals take more carbon dioxide from the atmosphere and convert it to oxygen, have high efficiency of water use, require low input and hence are more environment friendly. Thus, millets can help to phase out climatic uncertainties, reducing atmospheric carbon dioxide, and can contribute in mitigating the climate change [1]

The tribal farmers of Koraput cultivate finger millet in the uplands as a sole crop or also as a mixed crop with other minor millets, pulses, maize and oil seeds. Koraput district of Odisha has warm and humid climate with 80% of the total annual rainfall received from the south-west monsoon in the months from June to mid-October. The annual average rainfall varies between 1320 and 1520 mm. The mean daily maximum temperature is around 40°C and minimum temperature is around 14°C. The major soil type is red lateritic soil (Alfisols), mixed grey soil (Inceptisols) and unaltered soils with coarse parent materials (Entisols). The prevailing soil texture in the area is mostly sandy loam. Agriculture is primarily rainfed, and kharif (June–September) is the main cropping season.

Table.1: Benefits of millets in terms of sustainable agriculture and nutrition aspects

Millets: an approach for sustainable agriculture and healthy world			
Food Security <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainable food source for combating hunger in changing world climate • Resistant to climatic stress, pest and disease. 	Nutritional Security. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rich in micronutrients like calcium, iron, zinc, iodine etc. • Rich in bioactive compounds. • Better amino acid profile 	Safety from diseases <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gluten free a substitute for wheat in celiac diseases. Low GI. A good food for diabetic persons. Can help combat cardiovascular diseases, anaemia, calcium deficiency etc. 	Economic security <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Climate resilient crop • Sustainable income source for farmers in rain fed area. • Low investment needed for production. • Value addition can lead to economic gains.

Millet Cultivation in Koraput

Finger millet is a major staple food crop among the tribal community across the southern district of Odisha, second to paddy, among subsistence farming households in the rainfed uplands of the district. Area under finger millet accounts for 16% of the total gross cropped area and 28% of the total area under cereal crop cultivation in the district [2]. The tribal communities predominantly cultivate local landraces of finger millet, viz. telugu mandia, dasara mandia, san mandia and bada mandia, using traditional agronomic practices. Millets are mostly raised in kharif (June–September) on marginal lands in the upland and hilly regions with few or no external inputs, either as a pure crop or with a range of pulses, legumes and oilseeds under mixed cropping systems. Besides its importance as a nutritious food crop, finger millet contributes greatly to the incomes of rural households. It is sold directly as grain or brewed into local beer for sale in local markets where there is ready demand [2].

Despite great value associated with this nutri-crop by the local communities, there has been decline both in area and in production of the crop. The area under finger millet cultivation in the district declined by 55% over three decades, from 144,480 hectares in 1980 to 65,160 ha in 2013 (Pradhan et al., 2019). Further, due to traditional cultivation practices, the grain yield is as low as 4 qha⁻¹ under broadcasting method, and even with traditional transplanting methods yield, it is only 9 qha⁻¹ (Pradhan et al., 2019). Some of the primary reasons are poor crop management (use of low quality seeds, broadcasting method of sowing leading to low plant population, no nutrient and weed management practices), and in some cases replacement by commercial plantations of Eucalyptus; this has led to both reduced availability and consumption.

Farmers maintain local cultivars by continuously selecting seeds suitable to local agro-ecosystem. However, presently only three varieties of finger millets (Bada Mandia, Kala Mandia, and Bhairabi) are mostly cultivated. Among them, the Bada Mandia being most productive, dominates. Access to quality seeds and storage continue to be major constraints. All these factors have threatened

not only the millet eco-system but also accelerated loss of their genetic diversity and the traditional food culture associated with them. This article highlights the effect of different agricultural interventions for cultivation of millet and reviving finger millet trades among small holder farmers under the rainfed farming systems in Koraput district in South Odisha.

Methodologies

Different Agricultural Interventions in Millet Cultivation

System of Finger Millet Intensification (SMI)

Agro-ecological approaches like System of Rice Intensification aims to produce crops more efficiently and sustainably by depending more on endogenous processes than on external inputs. SMI practices included raising nursery, transplanting young seedlings, weeding by weeders and application of organic manures. Farmers were trained on seed selection, conservation and seed multiplication. The land is ploughed thoroughly 2 to 3 times within an interval of 8-10 days. Compost and Neem/Karanja cake are applied during land preparation. After ploughing, the field is leveled using a wooden leveler. Seed selection is done through brine water solution. Seed treatment is done by medicinal pot manure/Bijamrita. Micro-organisms and nutrients are added to make the seedlings more vigorous, resistant to pests and diseases. Raised seed bed is prepared by mixing soil and compost in 2:1 ratio. The seeds are put into the nursery soil at a depth of 1/2 inch, with spacing about 3 to 4 inches between the seeds. 15 kg of vermi-compost/powdered FYM is spread over the bed in a thin layer and covered with straw. Then seed bed is watered once in a day 15 days' seedlings become ready for transplantation.

Seedlings are transplanted from the nursery into the main field when they are only 15-18 days old, with mass of soil attached to the root and there is moisture in the field. The spacing is maintained at 25 x 25 cm using a rope marker. Farmyard manure and vermi compost are applied in the pits at the time of planting. First weeding is done within 15- 20 days after transplanting with a roller weeder or cycle hoe. Second and third weeding is done either by roller weeder or manually by hoeing as the soil is hard (due to the upland). Vermicompost, pot manure or Jibamruta solution is applied after each weeding. In order to control pests, medicinal pot manure or neem oil solution is sprayed. Harvesting became much easier as plant growth is more uniform and the mature fingers do not get entangled. The women found it easier to harvest the fingers in SMI field. They could complete the task in half the time as compared to time required in a traditional broadcasted field. Thus, there was less drudgery for women.

Line Transplanting

Line transplanting as like SMI practices included raising nursery, transplanting young seedlings, weeding by weeders and application of organic manures. Farmers were trained on seed selection, conservation and seed multiplication. The land is ploughed thoroughly 2 to 3 times within an interval of 8-10 days. Compost and Neem/Karanja cake are applied during land preparation. After ploughing, the field is level using a wooden leveler. Seed selection is done through brine water

solution. Seed treatment is done by medicinal pot manure/Bijamrita. Micro-organisms and nutrients are added to make the seedlings more vigorous, resistant to pests and diseases. Raised seed bed is prepared by mixing soil and compost in 2:1 ratio. The seeds are put into the nursery soil at a depth of 1/2 inch, with spacing about 3 to 4 inches between the seeds. 15 kg of vermi-compost/powdered FYM is spread over the bed in a thin layer and covered with straw. Then seed bed is watered once in a day. 20 -25 days seedlings become ready for transplantation.

Seedlings are transplanted from the nursery into the main field when they are only 20-25 days old, with mass of soil attached to the root and there is moisture in the field. The spacing is maintained line to line 8 to 10 inch and plant to plant 6 inch using a rope marker. Farmyard manure and vermi compost are applied in the pits at the time of planting. First weeding is done within 15- 20 days after transplanting with a roller weeder or cycle hoe. Second and third weeding is done either by roller weeder or manually by hoeing as the soil is hard (due to the upland). Vermicompost, pot manure or Jibamruta solution is applied after each weeding. In order to control pests, medicinal pot manure or neem oil solution is sprayed. Harvesting became much easier as plant growth is more uniform and the mature fingers do not get entangled. The women found it easier to do the inter cultural operation in the field as compare to tradition system.

Result and Discussion:

The average yield in SMI was 12-14 quintals per hectare which was more than double than the average yields from traditional method. This was a substantial motivating factor for farmers to adopt SMI, though initially farmers were skeptical that SMI is labour intensive. As transplanting facilitates inter-row and interplant weed control, farmers used weeding tools like roller weeder to incorporate the weeds into the soil, boosting fertility. Aerating the soil stimulated the growth of plant roots, making them strong enough to resist heavy winds. The result of the trial was striking to the farmers as there were 12- 18 tillers on an average and the best field of one farmer had 44-47 tillers per plant hill. The average yield was 21 quintals/ha, the highest being 34 quintals/ha. Also with the use of roller weeders, men started sharing responsibilities in weeding. Dependence on hired labour got reduced. The table 2 showed the average yield of different millet variety after cultivated in SMI techniques.

Table 2. Average yield of Finger millet in SMI and LT agronomic practices

Sl No	Name of the varieties	Yield in quintal per hectares (SMI)	Yield in quintal per hectares (LT)
1.	Sana mandia	19.83	16.80
2.	Bada Madia	21.82	19.73
3.	Jam Mandia	21.02	18.75
4.	Richika Mandia	19.43	18.30
5.	Mami Mandia	20.85	19.23
6.	Bhairabi	22.25	19.95
7.	Chilli mandia	21.75	20.50
8.	Bhalu Mandia	34.80	31.93
9.	Chilika Mandia	23.28	22.43
10.	Jana mandia	12.53	12.25
11.	Jandri Mandia	15.32	14.81
12.	ML365	26.70	25.78
13.	GPU-66	18.20	19.00
14.	Bati Mandia	25.08	24.43
15.	Arjuna	21.43	20.53

As Odisha Millet mission was initiated with collaboration with different NGOs and awareness interventions were conducted, for which farmers are now taking interest for cultivation millets in large scale basis. The scheme is promoted SMI techniques which were now adopted by the farmers of Koraput district. Increase in production has significantly contributed to the nutritional food security of a very vulnerable community, with small land holdings. For the farmers adopting SMI, there is now enough millet available for household consumption for the whole year. The yield increase has also generated surplus for sale. As the potential of finger millet market is expanding, the price has increased which thus ensuring better incomes. SMI is emerging as a solution not only to reduce the hunger gap, but also as an agro-ecological approach to address climate change conditions. High productivity, tolerance to climate adversities and reduction in drudgery for women are some of the contributing factors for the up scaling of SMI. The average production system highest shows in case of SMI in comparison to LT and Tradition methods. So that if promote the SMI process in case of millet cultivation definitely it will help to reduced drudgery from women in inter cultural process as well as increase the production level as indicated in the table no-1.

Conclusion

The average yield in SMI was 12-14 quintals per hectare which was more than double than the average yields from traditional method. This was a substantial motivating factor for farmers to adopt SMI, though initially farmers were skeptical that SMI is labour intensive. As transplanting facilitates inter-row and interplant weed control, farmers used weeding tools like roller weeder to incorporate the weeds into the soil, boosting fertility. Aerating the soil stimulated the growth of plant roots, making them strong enough to resist heavy winds.

The average production system highest shows in case of SMI in comparison to LT and Tradition methods.

So that if promote the SMI process in case of millet cultivation definitely it will help to reduced drudgery from women in inter cultural operation like weeding, harvesting process as well as increase the production level will help for food security as well as livelihood security of the tribal communities of Koraput.

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Data Availability Statement

The authors confirm that the data supports the findings of the study are available within the article and raw data supports the results are available with the authors will provide with request if needed. It is stated that the published publication includes all graphics and data collected or developed during the study.

Author's Contributions

All authors' contributions to the articles are indicated.

All authors are contributed to prepared the articles from design the experiment, data collection, compilation and preparation of the manuscript and finalised the draft.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research authorship/or publication of this article.

Ethics

There are no ethical issues with the publication of this manuscript

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